

Professionalism Urgency in Zakat Management to Increase 'Amil Welfare and Performance

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A. Abstract

Compensation/reward is given as a part of the evaluation of employee's contributions, both directly and indirectly, fairly and wisely. The reward/compensation is necessary for Amil Zakat Institution to attract potential applicants while keeping good employees, as well as to achieve a competitive advantage, increase productivity, and make payments according to the law, facilitate strategic objective, determine and strengthen the organization's structure.

Communication is an important aspect of Amil Zakat Institution. It has a big impact and should be ethical. Among the impacts are changing people's opinions and determining whether a person is good or bad; good communication allows psychological comfort for both its communicator and the communicant at the same time and a message that is delivered in optimism manner can encourage enthusiasm in making changes.

Amil Zakat Institution uses task analysis to determine the training needs for the new employees. While for old employees, performance analysis is used as a verification process to find performance deficiency and to specify training needed to improve the flaw.

Keywords: *Professional, Welfare, Communication, Training, Performance, Amil*

B. BACKGROUND

Profit and non-profit organizations can create value from the capital and human resources. In the global economy, intangible asset, such as human resources, almost reaches 80% of the organization value. Conversion from intangible assets to tangible assets results in a new representation of thoughts in the organization. In this process, generally, human resources are the part that contributes the excellence in competition. Because every organization has employees and leaders who handle the development and organization's climate so the organization can effectively process the human resources' development. An organization can develop both its human resources and the organization itself through the portfolio of the business unit, which are leadership and organization development, human resource development, and knowledge sharing.

The management of an organization should ensure that the organization report and its description represent the economic situation of the organization's performance including its risk factors. Integrity and compliance in the financial statement include laws, accounting, and regulations. Internal and external auditors help the management in assuring that the reports, its explanations, and risk management have complied with the existing rules. Organization management also monitors risks and verifies the actions taken to reduce those risks. Management also ensures that these operations are ethical with the costumers and employees.

In agreeing and monitoring its strategy, organizations generally participate to create and formulate the strategy and also implement the strategy in the long-term. The management of an organization is fully responsible to understand and approve the strategy. The organization's leader should continually monitor the implementation and the result of the strategy. The organization, in approving the financial decision in general, should ensure that financial resources are effectively and efficiently used to achieve the strategic objectives. Management of organization approves annual operation and budgeting.

Compliance and external communication are established through regulations and external communication as well as by ensuring that the external report and its explanation describe the organization's strategy. The planning and decision support includes analysis, consultation, and system that improve the management quality and organizations cross strategy.

Active organization management can create and implement a successful strategy. Management provide support on the organization's performance which covers several main responsibilities, such as ensuring the work process to maintain organization's integrity, including financial report's integrity, the integrity of relationships with the other stakeholders; selecting organization's leaders, evaluating the leader and senior executive team, and evaluating the performance of executive work; provide advice and support to the leaders.

Assessment of the training needs for the new employees is important for an organization, especially for the employees; to employ the inexperienced people and train them after being employed. The organization aims to improve employees' skills and knowledge to do their tasks. The skilled employees will be able to do sharp analysis for every phenomenon happened around them.

Selecting and choosing potential employees does not guarantee that the employee can work effectively. One of the reasons is because some people have no idea what to do or how to do some things. When an employee cannot work effectively, the organization should provide training, education, and mentoring for its employees. The training was carried out by also giving necessary information and background to new employees about what is important to achieve satisfying work. These programs can be started by giving a short informal or long formal introduction. In this training, the organization can explain additional information about salary, work hours, holidays, employee benefits, administration policies, daily routines, organization operation, security measurements and regulations, and facilities.

Without that basic information, new employees can make a long-term mistake, even the dangerous one. The training also includes a further explanation about workmates, so the new employees feel welcomed as part of the group, hence increase their productivity. Successful training should fulfill four main aspects: first, the employees feel welcomed and comfortable; second, the employees understand organization holistically (organization's past and present, culture, vision, and future); third, key facts such as policies and procedures, the employee should be clear about what they expect on the job and attitude; fourth, the employee should start getting used to with how the organization act and reacts on things.

In Islamic psychology, human behavior and motives are divided into three, which are: (1) *jismaniyah* motivation (biological motives), (2) *nafsiyah* motivation (psychological), and *ruhiyyah* motivation (spiritual). With *ruhiyyah* motivation which includes motivation and effort to fulfill transcendental needs, religion reality as meta-motivation also has the potential to be the motivation to do other several activities. Moreover, motivation to pray and seek for Allah's pleasure can also be the main motivation and Meta motivation for the employees in their activities, including worldly activities.

According to Wahbah Zuhaily, 'amil zakat is the committee of zakat, which is people who collect zakat. This committee requires honesty and understanding of the law of zakat (*fiqh*). Further, Wahbah explains, those who can be categorized as zakat committees are 1) the person who is assigned to take a tenth of zakat (*al 'Ashir*); 2) the registrar of zakat data (*al Katib*); 3) zakat dividers for the (mustahik people who receive zakat); 4) the guard (security) of the collected property; 5) *al Hashir*, the person assigned to collect the owner of the assets or the person who is required to issue zakat; 6) *al 'arif*, the person assigned to assess the assets of those who are obliged to pay zakat; 7) animal counters; 8) weighers; 9) zakat herders; and 10) each committee involved in zakat, besides *qadi* and authorities (state officials and employees) because they already have state salaries.

Amil Zakat has existed since Rasulullah SAW period. Rasulullah SAW once employed a young man from the *Asad* tribe named Ibn Lutaibah to take care of the zakat affairs of the *Bani Sulaim*. He had also sent 'Alī bin Abī Thālib and Mu'az bin Jabal to Yemen to become' amil zakat. This continued until Khulafā 'al Rāshidīn and subsequent generations. The 'amil zakat ' is entitled to a part of zakat, even though they are rich people, as a logical consequence of their task of collecting zakat funds and distributing them to the mustahik.

C. RESEARCH METHODS

This study used a qualitative method since it is relevant to the literature study. This study emphasizes more on the theoretical significance of the process, not the literature study that requires the analysis of empirical significance tests in the field. The data source of this study is books and journals related to zakat fund management.

Problems (questions) in this research are:

1. What is the management strategy of Amil Zakat Institution to improve Amil's well-being?
2. What is the management strategy of Amil Zakat Institution to communicate with 'Amil?
3. What is the management strategy of Amil Zakat Institution to provide training for 'Amil?

D. DISCUSSION

According to M. Quraish Shihab, 'amil term is people who manage zakat, whether collecting zakat, determining people who are entitled, look for them, or delivering and distributing the funds to them. While 'alaiha term gives the impression that those managers are carrying out their activities whole-heartedly that sometimes it causes fatigue. This is because 'ala word implies mastery and ability over something. The use of such phrase to designate zakat managers implies that they get part of zakat because of two reasons: first, their great efforts; second, because the efforts include the interest of zakat itself.

'Amil is one of the people who are entitled to receive zakat (*mustahik*). Because 'amil is the recipient of zakat, then 'amil is entitled to receive salary or wages from the zakat he manages. The amount of salary or wages for 'amil zakat in the Qur'an or the Hadith of Rasulullah SAW, is not explicitly explained. Because of this lack of clarity, the ulama finally decided to *ijtihad* (establish/determine). There are two methods used to determine the amount of salary and wages for amil zakat: 1) taking 1/8 part (12.5%) of the number of zakat assets collected, assuming that 'amil is one of the eight mustahik. A maximum of 1/8 is determined so that 'amil does not take other mustahik rights, then. 2) Using a minimum standard of amil's daily expenses at that time. However, it should still consider the amount of zakat collected, so that the poor do not get a smaller share than 'amil. In this case, the size of a regional standard salary, such as the provincial minimum wage and district/city minimum wage (MSE), should be considered for comparison.

The code of conduct of 'amil should make 'amil believes that zakat is a serious mandate from Allah SWT. This act should be managed with sincerity. The spirit of worship and devotion to Allah SWT should underlie the noble duty of managing zakat. Some behaviors that can be referred as the code of ethics' of amil zakat are: working sincerely because of Allah, making zakat shari'a as a management guide, serving *muzaki* and *mustahik* with sincerity, is polite and having a humanitarian spirit, especially in helping the poor, believing that competitions between institutions as a competition in good things so the mutual respects among institutions are maintained, always transparent and accountable, always improving themselves to increase performance from time to time, and praying for muzaki as a form of respect for people who have participated in helping others.

There are several reasons why zakat should be distributed through 'amil and not personally. The reasons are: 1). to reduce muzaki's selfishness who thinks that his properties are all his own, 2) to maintain the mustahik's pride because there will be no direct contact between mustahik and muzaki, 3) to bring equality, justice while reaching zakat target, 4) to avoid a sense of community injustice when large funds are given only several people, 5) to mobilize and utilize the fund for the strategic needs of the people. Furthermore, according to Djamal Doa, several benefits of distributing zakat through 'amil are 1) groups of people who feel weak and inadequate do not feel left alone, instead they feel they live among civilized humans who care and traditions that are mutually help; 2) The muzaki are more disciplined in fulfilling their obligations and the poor are taken care of better. 3) To prevent poor people from feeling like beggars. 4) Fund distribution will be more neat and orderly. 5) Allocation for the public interest, such as *fi sabilillah* (those who fight for Islam), can be channeled properly because the government knows the targets better. 6) Zakat can also fund the state. 7) Zakat can be used to manage and develop productive economic potentials of the people. 8) Prevent the awkwardness between mustahik and muzaki.

According to Qaradāwi, 'amil zakat or zakat manager requirements are: first, a Moslem; second, *Mukallaf*, which is a healthy-minded adult who is responsible and can take care people's affairs; third, is trustworthy and honest; fourth, know and understand the law of zakat and can explain zakat-related information to the public; fifth, can properly complete the tasks given; sixth, is sincere in doing his duty.

According to Didin Hafidhuddin, the characteristics of the Muslim work ethic are: *al-salah*, means giving good and benefits; *al-itqan*, means stability and perfectness; *al-ihsan*, means do the best and even better; *al-mujahadah*, means work hard and optimal; *tanafus* and *ta'awun*, means competition and helping each other; and respect time. *Ihsan* quality has two meanings and two messages, which are: (1) do the best that can be done. It has the same meaning as *itqan*; every Muslim is committed to himself to do the best in everything he does, especially in the interests of the Ummah. (2). To give a better meaning than the achievements or quality of previous work. It means one should continuously improve, while increasing knowledge, experience, time and other resources. This also includes increasing the quality and quantity of da'wah.

The position of 'amil in zakat management is as the responsible person who bears the obligation of Allah SWT and represents Rasulullah SAW as *iqamatu al dīn wa al siyāsah fī al Dunya* (uphold Islam and manage the world life). The 'amilin also carries the mandate of people to manage the zakat. In this case, they act as *niyabu al-Rasul* (representative of Rasulullah) in maintaining Islamic rule.

Developing organization and leadership means: running a development program for leaders, building team wok, helping organization synergy, creating an organization's work climate and value. Those included on themes are leadership skills development model, leadership development programs, successful planning, rotation planning and development of key employees, culture and values development, knowledge and practice sharing, and internal communication strategies for all employees. The performance management process in Amil Zakat in this program is defined by: first, motivating, rewarding and bonuses for individual and team performance. This program helps achieve individual and team performance goals, builds individual and team value aligns employees in an incentive and bonus system with objective strategies, and change management facilities.

Initiatives included in this theme are leadership skills development model, leadership development program, successful planning, the main employee rotation, and development planning, culture and value development, knowledge sharing and practice, and internal communication strategy for employees. The performance management process of Amil Zakat is defined as follows: first, by motivating and appreciating the employees by giving a reward for individual and team performance. This program helps achieve individual and team goals, builds individual and team value, align the employees in an incentive and bonus system with objective strategy and change management facilities.

Second, information technology portfolios for service sharing, continuous evolution and the importance of information and technology that offers chances to every organization to achieve performance breakthrough and competitive benefit through effective alignment for resources with Amil Zakat Institution's strategies. Every Zakat Institution should identify and submit a portfolio of request initiatives of the information and technology related to its strategy implementation. Several components should be fulfilled in technology information portfolio, such as human resources, such as business analysis and decision support: rank analysis practice, translating and sharing of information or knowledge. The transaction process: a system that deals with basic organization repetition. Infrastructure: sharing technology and management expertise that requires effective delivery and information used in the zakat receipt and distribution.

Third, the financial portfolio of service strategy has a financial function that is specifically and operationally responsible for the Amil Zakat Institution. These responsibilities include management of financial transaction such as payable accounts (debts), receivable account, salaries, reports, investor reports; management of internal and external inspection and connection between them, the board's reports, the monthly managerial reports and the budget reports on the receipt and distribution of zakat.

Several components related to the financial portfolio of service strategies include monitoring of transaction and its process: improvement of the transaction system structure and effectiveness, such as working capital management and risk analysis of business unit production assets and strategic risk management.

In selecting and evaluating the executive performance, the management of Amil Zakat Institution can decide and approve rewards given to the executive after evaluating the executive and giving incentives as well. The management can also protect employees and executives, for example in a death case, illness, or accidents. In providing suggestions and support to its management, Amil Zakat Institution, individually (by its manager), can use specific knowledge about industry and function and management expertise to provide guidance based on the history of Amil Zakat Institution based on the history and its competitive position. The management can also share knowledge, experience, and policy to the executives by describing the strategic opportunities and decisions of Amil Zakat Institution.

In recruiting and selecting its employees, Amil Zakat Institution can use a total compensation program to help to ensure that the payments given are sufficient or proper to attract the right people, at the right time, for the right job. When the employees think that the total compensation program given to them is unfair and externally competitive, they can leave the Institution for better options.

Some legal rules are relevant to the provision of compensation. Amil Zakat Institution must be aware to implement these rules in the compensation payment program. The Amil Zakat Institute strives to create a profitable and competitive culture and attractive workplace. By giving compensation, this goal can be achieved and can even advance the goals of the Amil Zakat Institution, such as rapid growth, survival, and innovation. Compensation systems can help determine the structure, hierarchy, and level at which - where certain managers can influence employees in line positions.

From the strategic point of view, external justice refers to the determination of the compensation position compared to the determination of the compensation position. Compensation administration policies include information that needs to be disclosed to employees, employee involvement in the development of plans and the process of resolving disputes.

In communicating, Amil Zakat Institutions implement four main functions, which are supervision, motivation, emotional disclosure and information. Communication acts to control employee behavior, where each Amil Zakat Institute has a hierarchy of authority and formal guidelines that must be followed by employees. The process of communication consists of several parts: communication source, encoding, messages, channels, decoding, receivers, and feedback. The communication source begins a message by coding a thought influenced by conditions such as skills, attitudes, knowledge and socio-cultural systems. The message is an actual physical product of the source coding in which the message is influenced by the code or group of symbols used to transfer the meaning, the contents of the message itself and the decisions taken in selecting and organizing the code and content. Channels are the medium in which the message goes; the media chosen by the source must determine which channels are used in formal and informal settings. Decoding is the process before the message is received by the target, where the symbols must be translated into something that can be understood by the recipient of the message. Feedback is done to evaluate how successful the transfer process, whether it can be understood or not.

The communication can flow vertically or laterally. Vertical communication can be divided into downward and upward. Downward communication means it flows from one level in the Amil Zakat Institution to the lower level. This kind of communication can be used by a manager when deciding goals, giving work instruction, informing policies and procedures to his subordinates, pointing out problem highlight, and giving feedback about the employees' performance. Upward communication flows from a level to a higher part in Amil Zakat Institution. This kind of communication occurs when an employee giving feedback to the boss, informing goal progress or existing problems. Lateral communication happens between equal work teams or groups, or between managers that are at the same level. This communication can save time and simplify coordination.

Restructuring effort is characterized by uncertainties and changes which may arise a lot of fear and concern for the employees. After the information is transferred or channeled, information can also be delivered

through face-to-face communication style. Open communication with employees in which the executive, as people who understand the needs and concerns of the employees, is needed. An organization with effective employee communication will not be bothered by bad news.

Communication can also be done by making an open and equal room, by putting everyone involved to work together in a large room without barriers. Individuals of different functional groups in a team can be located in a large same room to encourage open communication and teamwork. To strengthen communication and teamwork, the team can also publish information about their activities in a certain wall intended as a 'current-situation' space so everyone can see it. This process is known as visualization.

In Islamic point of view, communication ethics mean exploring the intricacies of values about the ethics of communication in the Qur'an and as-Sunnah, to further influence and encourage people to apply these values for the good of oneself while providing maximum benefits for universal humanity. The communication ethics according to Islam are: be careful of our words coming from our speech, only speak good words, give priority to older and senior people, speak friendly and avoid being rude, be consistent between words and deeds, and speak no word except the truth (valid data), and do not fear other's critics, and also be brave to say what is right even it is not in line with what is applied in the community.

Training for the employees refers to the methods used to provide employees the skills needed to do a task. In the past, this kind of training only emphasized technical skills, but now this training also plays an important role in the performance management process of the Amil Zakat Institute. Training is an integration process used by the Amil Zakat Institute to ensure that employees' work is in line with their goals. An integrated approach can be implemented and the training is aimed to assign, train, evaluate, and give rewards to the employees. When the Amil Zakat Institution implements a performance management approach, it means the training given for the employees should be following the desired goal of the Amil Zakat Institution so both can reach the goal.

The training program consists of five steps, which are: the first step is the analysis step, which is finding out specific work skills needed, analyzing the skills and the needs of the employees and developing specific measurable knowledge and the goals. The second step is planning instructions to decide, arrange, create, and also learn the training program that uses hands-on training. The third step is validation, which involved people holds a training program and presents it to the training participants. The fourth step is applying for the program by training the targeted employees. The fifth step is evaluation and follow-ups. In this final step, the management evaluates the success or failure of this program.

Several methods that can be used to identify the training needs for old employees are by looking through performance report from superiors, coworkers, or the employees themselves; or looking through other data related to the performance including productivity, the absent and late counts, accident and short-term illness list, complaints, late deliveries, product quality, time inactivity, repairs, equipment usage, and customer complaints; supervision by supervisor; interview with supervisor; examinations related to the job knowledge, skills, and attendance; behavior surveys; employee daily agenda and training center.

On-the-job training is done by asking someone to learn the job by directly by doing it. Every employee does on-the-job training when the employee joins the organization. On-the-job training is widely applied in Amil Zakat Institutions. This training is the most known training, by direct-coaching or understudy method (while learning). Internships are carried out in a structured process to produce skilled employees through a combination of classroom lessons and on-the-job training, and this is widely used to train several jobs.

Many jobs consist of a series of logical steps taught gradually in stages. This gradual process is called Job Instruction Training (JIT). This process should begin by presenting steps needed in each work and each step should be done in the right sequence. These steps show what needs to be done and it is important to show how and why it is done. Teaching can be done in a fast and simple way to provide knowledge to trained employees. Although some people say this teaching method is boring, this method is quite effective.

Simulation training is a method in which the trained employees are trained to learn with the actual equipment or with simulations that will be used on the job, but the training process occurs outside of work. This training is necessary when it is too expensive or dangerous to train employees at work. With computer-based training, employees are trained to use computer-based systems to interactively improve their knowledge or skills.

Off-the-job training and development techniques can be carried out by, for example, case study methods, management games, outside seminars, programs related to education, role-playing, behavior modeling, and executive training. The case study method is for managers to describe in written organization problems and provide a solution. In the management game, a development technique is given in which managers compete by making computerized decisions about realistic simulation situations. Outside seminars are provided by many organizations and colleges that offer web development seminars and conferences. Role-playing is done by inventing training techniques where the person trained plays a part in a realistic management situation. The modeling of effective actors is done by first show good management techniques to trained employees in a film, then asked them to do a simulation to be given feedback after. Many Amil Zakat Institutions use executive training to develop effective top managers. Executive training is conducted by consultants from outside the Amil Zakat Institute interviewing executive leaders, coworkers and subordinates to identify strengths and weaknesses of the executive ranks and provide advice to executives so that they can benefit from strengths and overcome weaknesses.

Work examining can be done by asking the employees to demonstrate basic skills in doing work and explain the stages of the job. Managers can assist and correct their mistakes while explaining every step should be taken by the employees. When placing an employee to a job, the support can be given after the employee shows they are skilled to do the job, both receiving and distributing zakat funds.

E. CONCLUSION

The strategic theme reflects the management's trust that needs to be carried out to achieve the success of the Amil Zakat Institution. The strategies that must be taken for Amil Zakat Institution to achieve Amil professionalism are:

1. Strategies to improve the welfare of Amil Zakat can be done by motivating, giving rewards and bonuses for individual and team performance. This program helps achieve individual and team performance goals, builds individual and team value aligns employees in an incentive and bonus system with objective strategies and change management facilities. Information technology portfolio consists of service sharing, sustainable evolution and the importance of information technology that offers each organization the opportunity to achieve breakthrough performance and competitive advantage through effective alignment of resources with the strategy of the Amil Zakat Institution. The financial portfolio consists of service strategies, financial functions specific and operational responsibility.
2. In communication, Amil Zakat Institution implements four main functions, which are supervision, motivation, emotional disclosure, and information. Communication acts to control employee's behavior because every Amil Zakat Institution has a hierarchy of authority and form guidelines that must be met by the employees.
3. The training strategy of Amil Zakat Institution should pay attention to: first, analysis of needs to find out the specific work skills needed, analyze the skills and needs of employees to be trained and develop specific measured knowledge and objectives achievement; second, planning instructions to decide, arrange and produce the contents of training programs that use techniques with hands-on training and learn them; third, validation in which the people involved make a training program by presenting it to several training participants; fourth, implementing programs, which is provide training for targeted employees; fifth, evaluation and follow-up, in which the management of the Amil Zakat Institution assesses the success or failure of the program.

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